

The Divine Currency of the Goddess: Impact of Durga Puja on the Economy of West Bengal

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Abstract: This article explores the role of Durga Puja in the economic dynamics of West Bengal. With massive business transactions before and during the festival and entire creative industries built around the annual five-day festival, Durga Puja is one of the largest contributors in the economy of West Bengal. It is, therefore, common and reasonable to refer to this phenomena as the 'Durga Puja Industry'. We have discussed different components that make up the huge business transactions and provide employment to several people every year. We have tried to put this economic powerhouse of present day West Bengal into historical context, and the evolution of the Goddess' tradition as the creator, the provider and the protector of the universe; as deity of the crops and the merchant.

Keywords: Durga Puja, Durga Puja Economy, Durga Puja Revenue, Pandal, Kumartuli, Durga Puja Footfall, Durga Puja Employment, Durga Puja GDP Share, Living Goddess Traditions.

ahaṃ raṣṭri saṃgamaṇi vasuṇaṃ cikituṣi prathama yajñiyam |

taṃ ma deva vyadadhuḥ purutra bhuristhatraṃ bhuryaveśyantim ||

(I am the Queen of the Universe; I give wealth to those who worship me. I am the all-knowing one and the prime one among the worshippable deities. I enter many bodies as the Atma, taking various forms and with different manifestations, in various ways. Hence, the Devas have incorporated me in various places.)

- Verse III, Devi Suktam, Sukta 125, Maṇḍala 10

The Sharadiya (Autumnal) Durga Puja is a festival commonly celebrated in eastern parts of India and Bangladesh, Nepal as well. Out of a number of regions that claim to observe Durga Puja, the festival has reached the pinnacle of popularity and splendour in the Indian state of West Bengal.

Also known as Durgotsab or Sharodotsab, Durga puja is the biggest festivity of the year in West Bengal among these places, and is a key factor controlling the economy of this Indian state. Such is its importance that the festival is often considered essential to the identity of Bengali ethnicity. Though there is a common misperception prevalent among the intellectuals about Durga Pujo being just a Hindu religious ceremony restricted within the ‘upper class’ which hardly concern the ‘masses’, the reality is quite the opposite. Not only is Sharadotsab supposed to be a largely public event encompassing all boundaries of age, gender, poverty, caste and creed as far as the excitement and rituals and rites are concerned, it presents a unique opportunity to stand firm on a strong economic footing to many. Since the late medieval period, most of the Durga Puja celebrations were organised by personal or family initiatives. But the last century brought a major change in socio-cultural dynamics of Bengal, in the aftermath of which Barowari pujas, the pujas organised by community associations, started taking over. According to a 2018 estimate by the government, there were more than 28,000 barowari (community) pujas in West Bengal in addition to the ones conducted by families in a somewhat private ceremonial manner. Among the barowari ones from all over the state, nearly 40% are in Kolkata. Needless to say, the numbers increase every year, as more and more new organisers gather enough resources to arrange an annual gala on the occasion of Maa Durga’s worship. While the Pujas conducted in temples or family homes are somewhat more orthodox, sincere and ritual-centric, the barowari celebrations organised in temporary marquees or ‘pandals’ have a lighter mood, bigger stature and spontaneous public participation. Executing an event of this scale is, indeed, more often than not a demonstration of wealth and authority of the organizers, which explains the inclination of noteworthy politicians and business tycoons to be in touch with organising a Durga Puja. It would be hard to name another festival from anywhere in the world which has considerable significance at so many different dimensions.

Durga Puja has, in fact, been full of grandeur throughout history. According to Asko Parpola, animal sacrifice rituals have been an integral part of goddess-worship since Indus civilization. Such sacrifices are always associated with a rise in livestock trade and charitable distribution of animal meat among devotees. Larger the scale of the ceremony, higher was the number of animals sacrificed. Donation to the needy in cash and kind has also been a part of Puja. The family Durga Pujas of 19th century Babu households even came with days-long performance of Kobigaan, Kirtan, Jatra and more, accompanied by special parties for Europeans. Just as today, the Pujo income would help the artisans thrive through the year. According to personal accounts of some of the East India Company officials who visited such Pujos, the expenditure of one such ceremony could vary between 25-70 lakh rupees at the time. Going back in time, one must mention Raja Kamsanarayan of Taherpur, who is often credited with reviving Durga Puja of Bengal to its ancient glory in 16th century after a period of devastation brought in by waves of Turkic invasions. It is said that Kamsanarayan wanted to conduct something that resembles the glory of a Vedic Ashwamedha, but was suggested to conduct Durga Puja instead by the Brahmins of his court, who announced that Durga Puja is the Ashwamedha of Kaliyuga. With the ideal of Ashwamedha as described in literature in his mind, the Raja conducted a Durga Puja that became a fable. Legend has it that he spent about eight lakh rupees at the time.

A 2013 report by ASSOCHAM (The Associated Chambers of Commerce and Industry of India) titled ‘West Bengal Cashing In On Durga Puja’ estimates the size of the Durga Puja industry as about Rs. 25,000 crore (USD 5 billion). The economic worth of the festival was projected to grow upto Rs. 40,000 crore by 2015 in the report, with a compound annual growth

rate (CAGR) of 35%. Somewhat based on this, contemporary media reports estimated the size of the Durga Puja economy to be about Rs. 1,00,000 crore in 2018. Whereas, the GSDP of West Bengal was approximately Rs. 10,48,678 crore in the same financial year. Hence the contribution of the Durga Puja as an industry to the GSDP of the state is nearly 10% as per the figures from FY 2018-19, which is certainly an overwhelming amount for a five-day festival. Since it involves such major monetary transactions, the industry is one of the largest employment-generators in the state as well, providing jobs to 4-lakh-odd people for almost six months every year. Most of the community or barowari pujas usually employ at least 20-25 people every year during the event, the count shooting up to a 50-odd figure in case of some of the largest ones. As the economy recover from the blow of COVID, the Pujo economy of 2025 has managed to cross a satisfactory 65000 crore mark, falling short of the projected 70000 crore estimate after incessant rains and early timing this year. The much-heard hue and cry about 'wastage of money and resources in useless grandure in the name of festival' sounds fairly hollow in the backdrop of these figures.

The carnival comes with a sudden increase in flow of money in the market. Most public and private sector employees of the state receive their annual bonus (or the 'Puja Bonus' as commonly known in West Bengal) or festival advances just before the Puja, which boost the consumer spending. The traditions associated with Durga Puja include shopping and exchanging gifts, particularly clothing, days before the ritual celebrations start. So there is always a boom in sale of garments, jewellery and other accessories in West Bengal right before the onset of Durga Puja. A 1954 report of The Economic and Political Weekly titled 'The Economics of the Durga Puja' had noted that the Durga Puja shopping is one of the best indicators of people's incomes in the state. While a smooth flow of liquid cash in the consumer market shows quite a craze in pre-Puja shopping, economic slowdown or recession-like conditions have been observed to hamper these activities very clearly. In the past years, peaks and troughs have been noticed in pre-Puja sales of retail stores depending on these factors. For example, apparel brand Pantaloons gained a growth of over 30% in West Bengal during Durga Puja in 2018. Whereas, the Hindustan Times reported an estimated 30-40% shrinkage in pre-Puja sales in retail markets spanning both big stores and roadside hawkers the following year, presumably indicating to the contemporary economic slowdown. COVID had considerably affected all sectors, thereby almost stopping the growth. But in the years following lockdown, we are slowly catching up, although with a major change in the shopping preferences. A huge section of the activities is now centered around the e-commerce platforms, even at the expense of roadside hawkers and small business owners. Specifically, in 2025, they have suffered a huge loss as a result of the sudden rainfall and waterlogging conditions compounded with a growing popularity of online shopping trends, standing at an estimated 20% dip from last year. But malls and outlet chains are quite well-off in comparison.

The center of attraction of the festive season is the marquees or 'pandals' set up for the celebrations. From mere structures of bamboo frame covered with tarpaulin and decorative canvas housing the Goddess's idol to gigantic pieces of art showcasing innovation, intricacy, complexity and efficiency at its best, the pandal culture has evolved a lot. According to a 2019 study conducted by experts from the British Council, Indian Institute of Technology Kharagpur and Queen Mary University(UK), the creative industries operating around Durga Puja amounts to Rs. 32,377 crore(USD 4.53 billion). This is around 2.5% of the contemporary GSDP (Gross State Domestic Product) of West Bengal. While the budget of a more traditional and low-key

puja can be around Rs. 15-20 lakh, that of a pompous mega-pandal with beautiful decorations and grand celebrations can reach upto Rs. 2-3 crore. Most of the budget is allocated for pandal and the idol to be housed in it. A report by The Indian Express expected the size of the pandal industry to grow by 35% and touch Rs. 500 crore in 2013 from the Rs. 350 crore estimate of the previous year's transactions on this field. As of 2025, the estimate of expenditure on idol, decorations and illuminations stand at a handsome 450 crore-odd amount for the whole state, with Kolkata alone contributing to about half of it. To take a closer look at what involves such big money, let us list out some of the key steps in setting the stage for the carnival. The Puja Committees conduct the khuti pujo ritual about 2-and-a-half months before Durga Puja, in order to sanctify the site and skeletal structure of their upcoming pandal. Soon after, raw materials such as bamboo, tarpaulin and cloth are brought to the site and the construction begins. Meanwhile the pottery craftsmen work day and night to finish the idols which are made of clay layering over bamboo and hay frames. Just a day or two before the Puja, when the pandal is nearly finished, the idol is brought from the artist's workshop to the pandal and installed there, though it is supposed to remain curtained until the festival actually begins. The lightings and decor all over the surrounding locality follow the suit right away. Each of these steps require several hands, and of course a lumpsome amount of money. As the popularity of 'theme pujo' increased over the years, the pandals have become more and more decorative, artsy and full of new ideas. To keep pace with the vibes of the respective pandal, the making of idols are often improvised. The lightings and other nuances of decoration have been touching new heights every year. As a result, fresh skills, improved professionalism and efficiency and groundbreaking ideas have entered the industry. The expenditure broke all previous records as well. Given the incentive provided by awards given out to the best of the organizers by Government and non-Government initiatives and the subsequent media attention, the 'theme' race is unlikely to die down in near future, which implies a promising future prospect of this industry. The idol-makers have been true benefactor of strengthening of the Puja industry. Many of them has come to the limelight by creating first-of-its-kind idols, winning prizes and setting up new records. They have been able to broaden their market base through the attention thus received and a gradual shift to modern methods and concepts while maintaining the traditional essence of the craft. Artists like Mintu Pal, who built many famous idols in recent years including the 2015 Deshapriya Park pandal and idol have received worldwide acclaim. As the Bengali diaspora residing in regions outside eastern part of the Indian subcontinent has gained momentum, the fervour of Durga Puja has crossed international borders and the communities in several countries have started celebrating the festival. This has helped the craft reach international stages as well.

The Durga Puja rituals continue for five entire days and includes offerings and sacrificial rites along with chants and arati at different hours of the day. Apart from the priests chanting mantras and excerpts from different sacred texts, performing arati, hom, bali and other rituals from time to time, Dhakis are an integral part of Durga Puja. Playing the dhak during each of the rituals in the specific beats associated to the ritual is a must. For this, the dhakis, who usually inherit the profession of playing the drum native to Bengal from their forefathers, are hired by organisers of each Puja beforehand. Thousands of priests and dhakis find the most high-paying appointments of the year during Durga Puja. Goddess Durga is often associated with harvest and vegetation as the mother goddess Shakamvari and worshipped in the symbolic form of Nabapatrika(the nine plants). Also, the rituals require a bulk of garlands and loose flowers including some specific ones for specific rites, viz. marigold, lotus, china rose etc. For one,

lotuses are very important in Durga Puja rituals, and according to a 2018 estimate by the flower cultivators of West Bengal themselves, there is a requirement of around 50 lakh lotuses in the state. Lotuses from Bengal are also exported to other regions, where its demand is high because of superior quality of the produce. This is, in its true sense, a tribute to the agricultural sector—both symbolically and in practice. In Pujas which are set to a more traditional note, like those of villages, small towns, temples or family homes, some devotees, though depleting in number, like to offer animal sacrifice to the Goddess. Others, however, prefer to go with just a symbolic sacrifice of a vegetable, or live fish. Along with the usual Bhog (food offerings presented to the Goddess), the sacrificial meat is distributed among the devotees present. Many devotees, albeit with a bit of a showboast of their affluence, donate new clothes for the needy, or arrange for feasts on this occasion. Evidently, Durga Puja is not just a cultural event or a corporate battleground—rather a socio-economic bonanza that brings together the richest and the poorest in festivities in the name of the Mother.

The Bijaya Dashami, last day of Durga Puja, brings an array of celebratory rituals. As the time of bidding adieu to the Goddess comes closer, devotees try to inhale the last traces of the festive air as much as they can. After the completion of the final rituals, including offering sweets and Paan to Goddess Durga as a farewell gesture, amidst the devotees busy in enjoying Sindurkhela, Dhunuchi Nach, the loud blowing of Shaankh and the maddening beats of the Dhak, the Goddess's idol, along with those of her four children, proceed to the river Ghats for immersion (Bisarjan or Niranjan) on trucks. A long procession of devotees, often dancing crazily to the beats of Dhak and music from loudspeakers carried with the procession, follow the Goddess to the Ghat, to see her off. After the immersion, as soon as the clay layers of the idols wash away in the flow of the river, the bamboo-and-hay frame that was inside is taken out of the water using cranes and sent to the manufacturers again for recycling in the next Pujo. Though the use of paints containing lead and other hazardous materials on idols are causing a headache these days, an effort to replace these paints with eco-friendly ones is in place and organizations and individuals are trying their very best to spread awareness on this among the craftsmen. Eventually, this can yield the most eco-friendly way to celebrate the most elaborate and carnivalesque of religious festivals with a positive effect on economy. Also, the tradition dictates a visit to the house of near and dear ones after the Baran and Niranjan of the Goddess to indulge in greeting each other, exchange of sweets, a casual chat and sometimes, a sumptuous feast. As a result, food items, namely sweets, are on high demands on Bijaya Dashami. In spite of the sorrow of the departure of Maa, the last flames of festivities light up hearts before it blows out, leaving the devotees in a painful longing for the next year, who shouts out “Aaschhe bochhor abar hobe” (“It will happen next year again”).

Coming to the greater cultural impact of Durga Puja, the Sharadotsab always brings out the refinement of the quintessential Bengali Bhodrolok. Cultural programmes organised by the residents are part and parcel of Durga Puja celebrations. The Puja Committees also arrange for on-stage cultural performances in the pandal premises sometimes. Also, to dive into the excitement and anticipation for the upcoming festival, many musicians release albums and new compositions right before Puja. In today's age of virtual media, the artists from other branches of performing arts also find a chance to stage their performances in front of a wider audience. Art galleries organise exhibition of new artworks and even photography competitions. All the performances and exhibits though, are largely themed on the Puja and the Goddess. This, of course, presents a great opportunity for the artists to publicize their talents and even gain

economically, as the festive mood sets in and the masses have money to spend. The past years have seen many performers climb up the peaks of popularity starting from their Durga Puja hits ('Pujor Gaan'). The film industry also relies on the Pujo rush. Especially in the Bengali film industry, a number of movies are released every Pujo to catch the strong winds of the Pujo economy in their sail.

The Durga Puja celebrations have a truly carnivalesque stature. Naturally the participation is huge. The footfall in each of the prominent puja pandals in Kolkata is around 2-3 lakh per day. The Deshapriya Park pandal though, recorded an average of about 6 lakh visitors per day in 2016, owing to their very unique theme of a thousand-handed idol of the Goddess, and their 2015 track record. This creates a unrivalled opportunity for business houses to maximise their visibility in the consumer sphere. Consequently, the popular pujas attract large corporate sponsorships and contracts for outdoor advertising of different brands around the pandals. The Puja Committees also rent out kiosks near the pandal for vendors, specially those dealing in food and beverages. Over the years, there has been a paradigm shift from organizing pujas by raising fund with chanda (donation or subscriptions) from local residents to pivoting on sponsorships and rent for commercial space in the pandal premises. The latter now accounts for almost 90% of the funding required for the gigantic arrangements of Durga Puja in most cases. The corporate spending in Kolkata's Durga Puja amounts to about Rs. 500-800 crore, of which nearly Rs. 150 crore goes in advertising through banners and hoardings. The brands engage in a quite a battle over getting enough views in exchange of the money they invest on pujas, thereby inventing unprecedented advertising strategies quite often. A fine example of this sponsorship rush is the Durga idol's Rs. 6.5 crore saree made of 22kg of 22-carat gold at Santosh Mitra Square Puja Committee's pandal in North Kolkata in the year 2018. It was fully sponsored by a leading jewellery brand of the state and drew a lot of attention. The same pandal housed a 12-feet tall idol covered with gold plates costing around Rs. 17 crore the following year, again sponsored by a famous jewellery brand. There have been multiple instances of beverage or food product companies tying up with organisers to serve their product during bhog distribution in the pandal, or apparel brands providing T-shirts with their logo on it to dhakis for wearing while playing their dhak in the pandal. Some major brands have even started award ceremonies for the best Durga Puja in various categories, in which Asian Paints Sharad Shamman started in 1985 is regarded as the pioneer. This although, has proved to be a groundbreaking initiative in changing the ambience and stature of Durga Puja into a mega-show of artistic endeavours centering heritage and traditions, apart from being just an unique publicity stunt. A discussion on preposterous advertising ideas in Durga Puja, though, would be incomplete without a mention of the Deshapriya Park Puja Committee's 2015 feat. Their pandal was styled as a 88-feet-tall Durga idol and the primary sponsor Star Cement advertised it as the world's tallest Durga statue, putting on hoardings and banners across Eastern India. The severe media hype brought in an unexpectedly enormous number of visitors and the police was eventually forced to block access to the pandal and lodged an FIR against the Puja Committee for violating regulations following a stampede-like situation that left several people seriously injured and traffic in South Kolkata in a standstill for a whole day. The company had spent over Rs. 50 lakhs on the pandal and more than Rs. 5 crore for its publicity, and apart from all the commotion, the Star Cement had succeeded in becoming the talk of the town. As the statue was seen making and breaking records, the organizers donated it to the state for the exhibit to be put on a permanent display at Eco Park, Kolkata, which ensured that both the organizers and the sponsors would be in the limelight for quite some time now. Evidently, being

able to capture the chance to be associated with some prominent Puja Committee returns more than the capital it takes from the standpoint of the business houses.

As for the roadside stalls and kiosks that sprout up at every corner of the streets during puja, they pretty much steal the show in terms of demand and profit. From multinational and regional brands setting up outlets for popularizing their products ranging from fast food, soft drinks, confectionaries and even toys, books or magazines to local vendors giving big brand names a neck-and-neck competition in sales, or even NGOs and political parties trying to reach out to the masses using the huge carnival crowd, Durga Puja has it all. The roadside vendors make a fortune worth their profit through the rest of the year in the frenzy of the festival crowd. The eateries and food courts serve to the brim of their capacity, yet the average waiting time in restaurants often cross a whole hour. Figuratively, the period from October to January generates as much as 45% of the annual restaurant business, a lion's share of the amount coming from the Durga Puja days. The big shots in the industry are now a days keen to seize the day utilising the love of food and carnival spirit of the Puja crowds. Themed restaurants, special dishes including traditional Bengali cuisine, discounts and combos come up every Puja. Takeaways and food delivery chains, too, follow close behind. Excise sales touch record heights each year. The Pujo revenue from restaurants stand somewhere between 1200-1500 crore this year, 60% of it being from Kolkata.

People travel more than usual during Puja, both in their locality and out of town. Beside the famous 'pandal hopping' dayouts, which are almost synonymous to Durga Puja for many, some often make use of the 'Puja vacation' to its fullest and take a break from the maddening city crowds. So the transport industry makes the run of the year in the festive season. Along with public transport vehicles like bus, Metro and local trains, cabs run day and night all over the city. Rental vehicle services find high demands as enthusiasts go on day-outs and even tours that take a little longer. Pandal tourism usually tops the wishlist. Cities, specially Kolkata, receive an overwhelming number of visitors on each day of Durga Puja. Not only from suburban localities around the city, people pour in from the entire state, and even from different parts of the country. There has been a recent surge in interest about Kolkata's Durga Puja among the international community as well, and international tourists have been coming to the event in increasingly bigger numbers since. In particular, as most of the prominent Puja pandals of Kolkata are easier to reach by the city Metro, an unprecedentedly high number of passengers avail the Metro every Puja. In 2018, the Kolkata Metro reported its highest-ever footfall of around 9.11 lakh on the Shashthi of Durga Puja. The other modes of conveyance also remain packed. Many devotees like to pay a visit to places of worship in the occasion of the auspicious fortnight of Durga Puja, some prefer to enjoy the flavour of heritage and pure devotion associated with Durga Puja in rural areas rather than being absorbed in the carnivalesque celebrations of the metropolis. Quite a few like to relax their nerves in the calm air of remote and unexplored tourist destinations. As a consequence, there is a boost in long-distance travelling and tourism-related industries during these days. Clearly, the new trend of showcasing the Kolkata Durga Puja for festival tourism is going to attract more and more tourists every year from all over the world. The inception of Durga Puja Carnival is expected to help the festival gain international attention as well, because of the presence of foreign delegates, tourists and extensive media coverage. West Bengal is taking advantage of the attention on Durga Puja to promote all of the state's main tourist attractions on the whole, which appears to be an efficient advertising strategy.

The Covid-19 pandemic has, indeed, made the Durga Puja industry suffer a lot. Corporate sponsorships have been somewhat trimmed down. In fact, last year, the RG Kar incident has delivered a huge blow to the festive spirit. The economy is yet to stand up on its feet after the fatal blow of lockdowns, unemployment and inflation rate has surpassed all records. Migrating out of state has become a compulsion for a large number of Bengalis. Since the Durga Puja industry interacts with a number of socio-economic parameters, it would be wise to expect a reflection of all this in the upcoming years. On the other hand, we can also expect that the Puja economy will continue to impact the overall growth of the state in a positive way to some extent, at least. How the Puja economy might turn out in the next few years is a question of great anticipation and interest.

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